

Nutritional Status of various Composts in Soil and their Impact on Mung bean Growth

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Abstract: Balanced and stable supply of nutrients throughout the life span is pre-requisite for the growth and development of plants. It, generally, varies from crop to crop but usually the plants require maximum uptake of nutrients during the early phases of their development. Composting is undoubtedly a very important as well as a primeval process. The practice of manure composting is as ancient as in biblical times and remained in practice until the mid-20th century. Pakistani soils are deficient in nutrients mainly in N and P and high yield seems almost improbable without organic amendments. So the present study was proposed that deals with the use of different composts singly and in all possible combinations and their effect on soil properties, nutrient availability and crop productivity were evaluated. All of the compost amended soils showed the highest values as compared to the control and all treatments were found significantly different. The results showed that as compared to the compost less soils (control) the amended soils enhanced the soil properties and make the nutrients readily available to plants. After the analysis of nutritional status of composted soil before harvest of mung bean the highest N, P and K values were obtained by PMC (1.1907 mg/kg), PMC + GWC (5.0113mg/kg) and PMC + FYMC + GWC (160.49mg/kg) respectively. The highest N,P and K values that were restored in soil after harvest of mung bean crop were obtained by PMC (3.0767mg/kg), PMC + GWC (1.0203 mg/kg) and PMC + FYMC (82.887 mg/kg) respectively. Regarding the plant agronomic factors viz: Plant Height, Fresh Weight, dry Weight, plant harvested from PMC+FYMC+GWC amended soils showed the highest plant height and plant fresh weight (61.167cm 61.167g respectively), whereas, FYMC (7.7000g) amended soil was found highest in increasing dry weight. In case of total NPK of Mung bean plant, Plants obtained from compost amended soils showed the highest N, P and

K contents from the soil received PMC+FYMC (1.6500mg/kg), FYMC (0.7533mg/kg) and PMC (1.5167mg/kg) respectively.

Key words: Mung Bean, Nutrients, Manure, Compost, FYMC, PMC, GWC, NPK.

Introduction

Soil degradation, an outcome of improper agricultural practices, is the physical, chemical and biological decline in soil quality, which is related to the decrease in soil organic matter, fertility, and structural condition. It had become a major environmental and agricultural concern worldwide (Lim *et al.*, 2018). Balanced and stable supply of nutrients throughout the life span is pre-requisite for the growth and development of plants. It, generally, varies from crop to crop but usually the plants require maximum uptake of nutrients during the early phases of their development (Jones *et al.*, 2011). Many commercial fertilizers are available and certainly work faster in order to fulfill these requirements but their irrational use is somehow deleterious to mother nature.

Composting is undoubtedly a very important primeval process. Organic amendments add nutrients plus organic matter, offering many more opportunities for improvement of soil physical, chemical and biological properties, important for accomplishment of soil retrieval programs (Larney *et al.* 2012). The practice of manure composting is as ancient as in biblical times and remained in practice until the mid 20th century when its importance was vanquished by the onset of chemical fertilizers industry (Larney, *et al.*, 2006). Manure contains nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium) in both organic and inorganic form that are completely unavailable for plants as only inorganic form of nutrients are consumed by plants. For the proper utilization by plants the organic forms must be mineralized into inorganic forms (Munyabarenzi 2014). As compared to manure, compost is odor less, stores well and also easier in handling. It is the process of natural breakdown and microorganisms mediated controlled decomposition of organic residues that alters the readily degradable raw organic waste materials into humic substances that are biologically stable (Cooperband, 2002). The slow nutrient release pattern of compost enhances the net primary productivity and reduces the need for constant application of fertilizer (Ryals and Silver, 2013).

Nitrogen-fixing legumes such as mung bean in soil after harvest and according to them these crops offer a sustainable cropping mechanism. The legumes are in symbiotic relationship with bacterium rhizobium. By forming root nodules they fix the atmospheric nitrogen. This fixation process is somehow directly proportional to the biomass (Gill *et al.* 2007; Yaqub *et al.*, 2010 and Ilyas *et al.*, 2018)

Pakistani soils are deficient in nutrients mainly in N and P and high yield is almost improbable without organic amendments. The current study deals with the use of different composts singly and in all possible combinations to evaluate and compare the effect compost amendments on soil properties, nutrient availability and crop productivity. Each compost has its own nutritional worth and can be applied signally or in appropriate combinations as per requirement of the soils. This study will be helpful for the farmer in accurately manipulating the composts by identifying their nutritional values in order to achieve a sustainable yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To ascertain the relative efficiency of composts selected during *in vitro* assessment, a trial was conducted on mung bean (*Vigna radiata*) crop. In green house trial, the soil (10 kg) from PMAS Arid Agriculture University farm area after grinding and sieving (2 mm) was thoroughly mixed with treatment combinations and filled in plastic pots according to the following treatment plan, replicated thrice in complete randomized.

1. Poultry manure(PM)
2. Farm yard manure (FYM)
3. Green waste (GW)
4. PM + FYM at ratio of 1:1
5. PM + GW at ratio of 1:1
6. FYM + GW at ratio of 1:1
7. PM + FYM, + GW at ratio of 1:1:1
8. NPK at recommended rate for mung bean

Soil and plant samples were drawn and analysed soil and plant NPK, plant height fresh and dry weights,

Total N

Colorimetric analysis for digested soil samples was used to calculate total N. 0.2 g of soil sample in separate digestion tubes, 4.4 mL of digestion mixture containing selenium powder, lithium sulphate and hydrogen per oxide was added and digested for 2 h at 360 °C until solution becomes colorless. Then 50ml of water was added and mixed thoroughly and allowed to cool. Then volume was made up to 100 ml and mixed. After the settlement, the clear solution was then calorimetrically analyzed for total nitrogen (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982).

Olsen P

In a flask five gram soil was added. Then 100 ml solution of 0.5 M of NaHCO₃ was poured into same flask, shaken for about 30 minutes and filtered through filter paper. Then 10 ml of filtrate was added in another flask with 1ml of 5 NH₂SO₄. The volume was increased upto 40ml by adding distilled water. 8 ml of Ascorbic acid reagent was then poured in to flask for color development. Readings were taken after 10 minutes by the help of spectrophotometer (Olsen and Sommers, 1982).

Extractable K

5 g of soil together with 33ml 1N ammonium acetate solution was added in 50ml centrifuge tube. The tube was shaken for five minutes. Then solution was subjected to centrifugation until the supernatant liquid was obtained. Supernatant liquid was then diluted with 100 ml of 1N ammonium acetate. The standard curve method was used to determine the K concentration in the samples. The curve was prepared from absorbance values of a series of K solution using flame photometer (Helmke and Sparks, 1996).

Crop Analysis

During the course of crop growth following parameters were measured

Plant height

Plant height was measured with the help of a measuring tape.

Shoot weight

Shoots was collected and weighed on a measuring balance. Their weight was recorded

Statistical analysis

The data was recorded and statistically analyzed by using ANOV techniques suitable for complete randomized design. Means were evaluated by using LSD test with level of probability at 0.05, when the F-values are significant (Jan *et al.*, 2009).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An experiment was carried out in plastic pots under natural conditions to evaluate the efficiency of different composts (alone and in combination) in comparison with commercial fertilizer as a positive control and with compost less soil as a negative control. And the data was analyzed by using CRD design

Nutritional status of composted soil before harvesting.

Table I showed the values of N, P and K obtained after sowing of mung bean in pot soil amended with different composts. Among 7 different compost treatments one treatment is held in reserve as control (soil without compost) and one treatment is with commercial fertilizer NPK.

Data revealed that the highest value of nitrogen was obtained from NPK with the value of 1.2513 mg/kg. And among different compost treatments the highest nitrogen value was obtained by PMC i.e. 1.1907 mg/kg which is somewhat a smaller amount in comparison with commercial fertilizer but greater than control. Whereas the least was obtained by FYMC + GWC as compared to control with the value of 0.2163 mg/kg. The effects of other composts PMC + FYMC(1.0037mg/kg), PMC + FYMC + GWC (0.9427 mg/kg) were found to be significant over control whereas other remaining treatments showed lesser effect than control.

Table I: N, P and K of pot soil before harvesting

Treatment	Total N (mg/kg)	Total P (mg/kg)	Total K
Control	0.7523 c	1.8333 f	84.127 f
Poultry manure Compost (PMC)	1.1907 a	3.0133 d	125.00 e
Farm yard manure Compost (FYMC)	0.7397 c	3.1367 d	150.25 b
Green waste Compost (GWC)	0.3704 d	2.6853 e	138.19 d
PMC + FYMC	1.0037 b	4.1067 c	123.65 e
PMC + GWC	0.3033 d	5.0113 a	143.92 c
FYMC + GWC	0.2163 d	2.4733 e	137.96 d
PMC + FYMC + GWC	0.9427 b	4.6900 b	160.49 a
NPK	1.2513 a	3.0000 d	152.00 b

Lots of researches have been done that support the idea of improving soil properties with the incorporation of compost into the soil. When incorporated into soil, compost is mineralized, thereby providing a sustained release of available nutrients for plants (Ngo and Cavagnaro, 2018). N is most

imperative element for the proper development of plants (Leghari *et al.*, 2016). Compared to the commercial fertilizers composted organic materials release nitrogen at slow rates (Al-Bataina *et al.*, 2016) which is obvious from our findings. The frequency of decomposition of the organic matter from composted manure determines the rate of inorganic N release to the soil depends on (Cambardella *et al.*, 2003). According to Chadwick *et al.*, (2000) most of the organic N in organic manures are mineralized to inorganic N rapidly, however others are chemically or structurally inaccessible, being recalcitrant

In case of P availability from amended soil, the data showed the compost less soil contains very less available P. Highest P value was obtained from PMC + GWC i.e. 5.0113mg/kg which is highest from both the commercial fertilizer NPK and compost less soil. Whereas in contrast FYMC + GWC (0.24733mg/kg) showed the least value of P among other compost amended soils but slightly greater in amount than control (1.8333mg/kg) and lesser than NPK application. The above data also showed that the availability of P in compost less soil is very low and the amendment of composts in soil triggers the P accumulation. Higher crop yield has been reported in fields where manures were applied compared to inorganic sources (Nikus *et al.*, 2004). P is bound in soil in the form of nucleotides, inositol phosphate and phospholipids (Turner *et al.*, 2002) so for their availability to plants they must be mineralized into an inorganic form (Chen *et al.*, 2006) and with regard to this Boateng *et al.*, (2006) and Iqbal *et al.*, (2016) found that among organic amendments PM was found to be the rigorous source of P that in turn will help full in increasing crop productivity and is also effectual in preventing the crop prone to soil borne diseases (Forge *et al.*, 2016)

With reference to the available K in amended soil, the combination of all kind of composts (PMC + FYMC + GWC) showed the highest availability with the value of 160.49mg/kg in comparison with commercial fertilizer NPK (152.00 mg/kg) and the control (84.127mg/kg). Whereas in contrast PMC + FYMC (123.65mg/kg) showed the least value of K among other compost amended soils but slightly greater in amount than control (84.127mg/kg) and lesser than NPK (152.00 mg/kg) application. All other composts showed the values in between them. These results suggest that the addition of compost in to soil subsequently increases the nutrients level of soil as compared to compost less soil. Redding *et al.*, (2016) and BarTal *et al.* (2004) that continued seasonal applications of moderate quantities of composts nutrients will result in steadily increasing availability of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium with successive applications. There are a very few studies on the availability of K from manure derived compost. Overall in present study, combined compost treatments (PMC + FYMC + GWC, FYMC + GWC, PMC + GWC, PMC + FYMC respectively) showed significantly higher K release than sole compost applications. As stated by Lu *et al.* (2014) and Wu *et al.*, (2016) composting is a bio-decomposition, self-heating and aerobic process of organic waste, and it has advantages over other strategies because it reduces the volume of waste by 40–50% and provides a product that can be used as a material for soil pollution remediation, as a soil conditioner or as a good-quality fertilizer and the pollutants are degraded by the active microflora (Zeng *et al.*, (2011). And in this study the compost less soil showed a very low availability of K (84.127mg/kg). Tran *et al.*, (2018) stated the report of Codling *et al.* (2002) that K availability was lower from poultry litter than from a chemical fertilizer because of less available K and low amount of K and similarly in this study among the

sole compost applications PM manure also gives the less K than FYMC and GWC respectively. GWC is also a very rich source of organic matter as well as nutrients if successfully recycled through composting (Basak, 2018).

Nutritional status of composted soil after harvesting

In this experiment we observed a significantly higher N concentration almost in every treatment after harvesting of mung bean than before harvest. Values are shown in table 2. Compared with the control and commercial fertilizer NPK, the PMC amended soil was found to conserve maximum nitrogen in soil after harvest with the value of 3.0767mg/kg, whereas PMC + GWC (1.6073mg/kg) demonstrated reduced value of N concentration as compared to other amendments but still higher than both the control (1.1740 mg/kg) and commercial fertilizer (1.3867 mg/kg).

Lots of studies support the idea of conservation of N by Nitrogen-fixing legumes such as mung bean in soil after harvest and according to them these crops offer a sustainable cropping mechanism (Gill *et al* 2007; Yaqub *et al.*, 2010 and Ilyas *et al.*, 2018). The present study revealed that the concentration of N in soil increased considerably after harvest than before harvest. Mohammad *et al* (2010) also observed an increased concentration of macronutrients especially N after harvest of mung bean because of the ability of root nodules to fix atmospheric nitrogen and improves soil fertility by establishing a symbiotic relationship with the nitrogen fixing soil bacteria. In comparison among single and mixed compost treatments single treatments showed almost maximum values of N as compares to combined treatments. Thangasamy *et al.*, (2017) also found nearly the similar results in his studies. He found poultry manure to be best as compared to other single and mixed treatments in his study. He also stated that the decrease in value may be due to mismatch between nutrient release, crop nutrient demand, and unbalance in the plant nutrient concentration.

Many studies have shown an increase in soil P with continual land application of manure. This study revealed that among compost amendments PMC + GWC amended soils showed the highest value of release of P with the value of 1.0203 mg/kg as compared to both NPK and control treatments whereas least amount of P release was

Table 2 N, P and K of pot soil after harvesting

Treatment	Total N (mg/kg)	Total P (mg/kg)	Total K (mg/kg)
Control	1.1740 h	0.3287 g	54.507 f
Poultry manure Compost (PMC)	3.0767 a	0.9390 b	68.357 d
Farm yard manure Compost (FYMC)	2.6463 b	0.6650 e	62.160 e
Green waste Compost (GWC)	1.9153 e	0.5407 f	57.457 f
PMC + FYMC	2.1080 d	0.8427 c	82.887 a
PMC + GWC	1.6073 f	1.0203 a	63.100 e
FYMC + GWC	1.7303 f	0.7567 d	70.097 cd
PMC + FYMC + GWC	2.4350 c	0.7430 d	72.947 c

NPK	1.3867 g	0.5167 f	78.667 b
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observed in GWC with the amount of 0.5407 mg/kg which is still higher than both control and NPK treatments. In comparison between single and mixed compost treatments, mixed treatments were found rich in P than single treatments. P is crucial for normal plant growth and its maturity as it regulates protein synthesis and besides improving the soil fertility, by their root exudates mung bean has the capability to make the soil bounded and highly insoluble calcium-bounded phosphorus accessible to plants as well (Asim *et al.* 2006 and Hussain *et al.* 2014). The inorganic fertilizers add macro and micro nutrients in soil but not organic matter whereas organic amendments offers both organic matter along with nutrients, furthermore contributing towards improvement of soil's chemical, biological and physical properties, which is central for the accomplishment of soil recovery plans (Larney *et al.* 2012). In this study PMC, singly and mixed, was found effective in releasing P. Results are shown in Table 2. Mottin *et al.*, (2015) and Weir and gentry (2016) also found that poultry manure compost has significantly increased nutrient levels in the soil, especially phosphorus (P).

Effects of organic manure application on K fractions are shown in Table 2. The data showed the compost less soil exhibit very less K. Highest K value was obtained from PMC + FYMC ie 82.887 mg/kg which is highest from both the commercial fertilizer NPK and compost less soil. Whereas in contrast GWC showed the least value of K among other compost amended soils ie 57.457 mg/kg but slightly greater in amount than control (54.507 mg/kg) and lesser than NPK application (78.667mg/kg)., the above data also showed that the availability of K in compost less soil is very low and the amendment of composts in soil triggers the K accumulation. Values are shown in table 2. Potassium is the regulator of plant metabolic activities and for some plant it is highly required. In this study results revealed that availability of K was considerably decreased after harvest of mung bean as soil K is present in the soil: exchangeable, non-exchangeable, fixed, solution and mineral or structural (Sparks, 2001 and Zhang *et al.*, 2017). Soil organisms usually require less amount of potassium than plants do. Therefore, most of the potassium is quickly released after the decomposition of organic residues and actively taken up by the plants (Parnes. 2013). In this study soils amended with PMC and FYM were found effective in releasing K in soil. As among single treatments as both FYM and PMC stored a considerable amount of K in soil even after the harvest of mung bean. There was more release of organically bound K from poultry manure following its mineralization to inorganic forms (Soremi *et al.*, 2017).

Effect of Different composts on agronomic factors of Mung bean

Table 3 Mung bean plant height, fresh weight and dry weight

Treatment	Plant Height (cm)	Fresh Weight (g)	Dry Weight (g)
Control	41.667 e	14.920 f	2.8233 d
Poultry manure Compost (PMC)	53.900 c	18.120 d	6.1203 b
Farm yard manure Compost (FYMC)	50.133 d	20.120 d	7.7000 a
Green waste Compost (GWC)	42.100 e	15.587 ef	4.5400 c

PMC + FYMC	58.333 b	23.360 c	5.6000 bc
PMC + GWC	48.833 d	18.957 d	5.0333 c
FYMC + GWC	48.467 d	17.653 de	4.8667 c
PMC + FYMC + GWC	61.167 b	26.427 b	6.4033 b
NPK	65.867 a	28.967 a	8.2000 a

Table 3 represents the values of agronomic factors viz. Plant height, fresh weight and dry weight. The samples to collect data were taken after germination. Three plants were randomly selected from each pot and tagged for all data recordings. The values obtained significantly affected the plant height, fresh weight and dry weight. Results shown that among the composted treatments the plant harvested from PMC+FYMC+GWC amended soils showed the highest plant height with the value obtained 61.167 cm which is a highest sum than control (41.667cm) but less than the NPK amended treatment (65.867cm). Whereas the least value was obtained by GWC i.e 42.100 cm which is less than NPK but still greater than control. Previous work has documented that compost enhances the plant growth (Duong, 2013). He also mentioned that as compared to the same amount of nutrients added, plant nutrient uptake from compost may be lower due to their slow release than the inorganic fertilizer, because organic from of nutrients must be mineralized into inorganic form before their uptake by plant and according to Sharma *et al.* (2017) their slow release also helps the crop in maintaining the soil fertility. Our results are also supported by the findings of Curtis and Claassen (2005) and Uzoma *et al.* (2011) that FYM helps in increasing the plant access to water with greater root proliferation and also that Cow manure is high in organic materials and contains nutrients that is very help full in improving the plant growth and production. And Table 4 showed that among single compost treatments FYM showed the greater sum than other single treatments.

With reference to the plant fresh weight, the combination of all kind of composts (PMC + FYMC + GWC) again showed the maximum fresh weight with the value of 26.427g but is slightly less in comparison with commercial fertilizer NPK (28.967mg/kg) and lesser than the control(14.920 g). whereas the least value was obtained by GWC i.e 15.587g which is less than NPK but still greater than control. The results showed that compost manure had great effect on vegetative plant growth. And in case of dry weight the results obtained from the total dry weight show that bean planted in the treated soil had higher dry weight; and total dry weights were lacking in in mung beans planted in the control experiment. According to Bhuma (2001) and Naikwade (2014) by properly manipulating the organic waste in the form of compost regulates the vegetative productivity as, besides the little amount of acquiring nutrients in comparison with fertilizers, the presence of growth promoting principles like enzymes and hormones along with plant nutrients make them crucial for enhancement of soil's fertility and production. Hillary *et al.*(2018) also reported a significant impact of compost on an increased plant height and biomass.

Total NPK of Mung bean plant

The NPK data for all treatments are displayed in table. 4 Our results showed that addition of soil amendments increased plant growth and yield of mung bean, and soil treated with other soil amendments significantly enhanced the seed germination

Table 4: Mung bean plant N, P and K

Treatment	Total N (%)	Total P (%)	Total K (%)
Control	0.3900 h	0.1300 g	1.0303 e
Poultry manure Compost (PMC)	1.5100 c	0.5233 d	1.5167 a
Farm yard manure Compost (FYMC)	1.1767 e	0.7533 b	1.2000 cd
Green waste Compost (GWC)	0.6600 g	0.3467 f	1.1553 de
PMC + FYMC	1.6500 b	0.6433 c	1.3433 bc
PMC + GWC	0.8440 f	0.4267 ef	1.1880 cde
FYMC + GWC	0.6127 g	0.5200 d	1.2300 cd
PMC + FYMC + GWC	1.3133 d	0.5003 de	1.2733 bcd
NPK	1.8267 a	1.1667 a	1.4367 ab

Plants obtained from compost amended soils showed the highest N contents from the soil received PMC+FYMC treatment ie 1.6500mg/kg. The value obtained was greater than control (0.3900mg/kg) but less than commercial fertilizer NPK (1.8267mg/kg). Whereas, the lowest value was obtained from FYMC + GWC ie. 0.6127 mg/kg which is less than NPK treatment but still greater than compost less soil. In comparison between single and mixed compost treatments N contents were found greater in mixed treatments. Among single treatments of FYM and PMC plants stored fairly good amount of N contents. In case of P the plants obtained from FYMC amended soil were found dominant in receiving highest P contents ie 0.7533mg/kg which is a greater amount than Control (0.1300 mg/kg) but less than NPK (1.1667mg/kg). Whereas least was obtained from GWC 0.3467mg/kg but still greater than compost less soil. In case of K single compost treatment was also found dominant. Highest K contents were found from PMC ie 1.5167mg/kg which is greater than both the compost less soil and NPK amended soil and the least value was obtained from GWC ie 1.1553mg/kg which is less than NPK amended soil but still a higher sum than control.

From the present study it was found that PMC and FYMC were found highly effective in storing NPK contents in plant even after harvest and these soils are responsible for higher yield than all other treatments. Meena *et al.* (2017) also stated that Farmyard manure and compost are great source of organic nutrients. Sen & Kumar (2012) also found that it is advantageous to apply various soil amendments in appropriate in order to maintains a healthy positive nutrient balance. He also observed a significant increase of yield in mung bean from amended soils than from control.

Conclusion:

Growing crops persistently in a land deprives the soil from their nutrients which directly affects the crop productivity. Therefore it is crucial to amend the soil with fertilizers to achieve a substantial nutritional status and to improve its physical properties. Many commercial fertilizers are available and certainly work faster in order to fulfill these requirements but their irrational use is somehow deleterious to mother nature.

It is concluded from the results that by properly manipulating the composted manure, not only the soils (deficient in nutrients) can regain their nutritional status but also a sustainable yield can be achieved. Each compost has its own nutritional value and can be applied singly or in appropriate combinations as per requirement of the soils. This study will be helpful for the farmer in properly manipulating the composts by knowing their nutritional values in order to achieve a sustainable yield.

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